

For the November planting, the varieties were generally consistent in duration between initial and 100% flowering, regardless of the magnitude of photoperiod sensitivity (Table 2). The exception was CN540, which took as long as 20 d to finish flowering. Lowland varieties sown after November, however, had different flowering patterns and the variety \times sowing date interaction was significant for duration to initial flowering, 50% flowering, and 100% flowering. CNM539 did not flower at all.

While time to flowering gradually decreased for IR42, Jaya, and IR36 in successive sowings, duration of Pankaj, CN540, and Mahsuri decreased from November to December but increased again in January. Though all other varieties flowered, none, except IR72, retained their flowering synchrony (a short interval between initial and 100% flowering) that simplifies harvesting. IR42 appeared to be the best variety with synchronous flowering behavior under all the sowing dates.

Flowering during mid- to late June for varieties such as Pankaj, Mahsuri, and CN540 is not conducive for higher grain yield. Long vegetative growth exposes the crop to the beginning of the southwest monsoon, often leading to lodging followed by seed sprouting. A good harvest with these varieties cannot be assured. On the other hand, the earliest variety, IR42, yielded comparably with Jaya and IR36. The advantage of IR42 is its long slender grain, which receives a premium in the market. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Vijetha: a high-yielding, short-duration rice variety for Andhra Pradesh, India

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Vijetha was developed from a cross between MTU5249 and MTU7014, using the pedigree breeding method at ARS.

Vijetha was highly promising in research station trials conducted during the 1991-94 dry seasons (Table 1). It yielded a mean 7.5 t ha⁻¹ and consistently produced at least 1 t ha⁻¹ more than check IR64—an average yield advantage of 22.8%.

In the All India Coordinated Trials during 1993 dry season, Vijetha re-

corded a mean yield of 4.9 t ha⁻¹ (Table 2) across 15 locations, indicating its wide adaptability.

At Maruteru, we used the seedbox technique to determine that the variety is resistant to brown planthopper (BPH), scoring a 3 on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale. Vijetha is also moderately resistant to gall midge (biotype 1), BPH, whitebacked planthopper, stem borer, leaf folder, and blast.

Vijetha is a semidwarf (105 cm) with dark green foliage and a broad, erect flag leaf. It possesses 8-10 productive tillers plant⁻¹. Flowering is completed in 3-4 d, contributing to uniform maturity. The panicle length is 26 cm and grains panicle⁻¹ total about 150; 1,000-grain weight is 24 g. The grain is medium-shaped and translucent, with a length-breadth ratio of 2.6 (length is 6.2 cm, breadth 2.4 cm). Dormancy ranges from 6 to 8 wk during kharif (dry

season). Milling percentage is 65.8%, with a 62.4% head rice recovery, and 5.0% broken rice percentage, classifying it as a fine-grained rice.

Results from 530 minikit trials conducted during 1994 and 1995 confirmed the superiority of Vijetha over check IR64 across Andhra Pradesh. Vijetha can be grown in either the wet season (145 d) or dry season (125 d).

It is a nonlodging, fertilizer responsive variety with resistance to several pests. Even before 3yr of minikit testing was completed, Vijetha was planted on more than 150,000 ha in Andhra Pradesh. Because of its outstanding potential, the State Seed Subcommittee released Vijetha in 1995. ■

Table 1. Yield performance of Vijetha at Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru, India. 1991-94 dry seasons.

Year	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		% increase over IR64	CV (%)	LSD (5%)
	Vijetha	IR64			
1991	7.5	5.6	33.9	11.3	0.9
1992	7.9	6.6	19.7	7.2	0.7
1993	7.7	6.2	24.2	13.0	1.0
1994	6.8	6.0	13.3	7.5	0.6
Mean	7.5	6.1	22.8		

Table 2. Performance of Vijetha at different locations in India. 1993 kharif.

State	Locations (no.)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹) ^a	
		Vijetha	Ratna (check)
Kerala	3	5.6	2.9
Tamil Nadu	3	6.5	4.8
Karnataka	2	4.8	5.4
Andhra Pradesh	3	4.6	4.6
Gujarat	1	3.5	0.8
Haryana	1	4.9	3.8
Uttar Pradesh	2	2.2	3.4
Mean ^b		4.9	4.0

^aMean of the locations in the state. ^bMean of 15 locations.